

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

ARtwin requirements specification

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to outline the requirements which are essential to meet the specific project objectives of the ARTwin project. This is included as part of Work Package 2 for the ARTwin project and is specifically the deliverable of Task 2.1. The requirements outlined in this document will then correspondingly drive the architecture specification, map pivot format specification, service implementation, platform development and implementation of the targeted use cases.

The specific project objectives, the project scope and other details pertaining to the project are elaborated in the following sections.

As the ARTwin project follows a use case driven methodology, the use cases are elaborated with the corresponding shortlisted user stories for the project as part of the System features section. The section describes the scenario of the workflows in depth and goes on to then describing the system level requirements which includes the functional, design and implementation constraints, documentation, requirements from specific external projects closely associated with the ARTwin project and assumptions and dependencies thereof. Non-functional requirements such as safety, performance, security and software quality guidelines have also been included as part of this document.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project Scope

In the industries today, digital Twins and BIM models need to be fully monitored and updated in order to not become obsolete. Furthermore, contextual and relevant information needs to be displayed to shop floor or factory personnel at the right place and the right time. Information needs to collate both that come from updated digital twins and BIMs and all other sources (production lines, integrated machinery, backend systems, supervisors, ...). However, current limitations hinder the achievement of these objectives. Some examples of such hinderances are 3D scans being very expensive, long and infrequently conducted and so on. Connected sensors on machinery are not reliable enough to provide up-to-date info. And most elements do not communicate with each other despite existent IOT.

Figure 1: ARTwin concept

To overcome these limitations, the ARTwin project aims to address the following objectives:

- Bridging the gap between physical and digital worlds
- Real-time maintenance of digital twins/BIMs based on vision sensors in factory and construction sites
- Provision of immersive and on-demand visualizations which are contextual and relevant
- Design and planning of new production lines or construction layouts through enhanced VR
- Integrating real-time information from multiple connected and communicating sources to alleviate field operator work
- Intercommunication amongst sensors by taking advantage of latest 5G and IOT domain technologies

- Making use of computing capabilities available on private clouds and their edges

The project does so by leveraging the ARCloud which computes and stores a complete cartography of real-world used for visualization and for accurate localization to help register virtual and real-world content on demand. Furthermore, the ARCloud delivers a platform to support the above objectives and services for device localization, digital twins/BIM update and AR remote rendering for low-resource devices.

Figure 2: ARTwin use cases

In line with the above broad project objectives, **3 demonstrators** will be implemented and tested in factory and construction sites indicated by Siemens and Artefacto respectively.

1.2 Basis for requirements specification

The requirements specification document was gathered as a result of interviews and research conducted with experts and key players in both AR&VR technologies and industries and factory site and shop floor personnel. The interviews provided a basis to further detail the use cases and thereby the requirements for the ARTwin project. The transcripts and any associated data supporting the requirements are shared with the partners. The sample interview consent form is attached as part of Appendix B.

Regarding construction sites, the requirements specification is guided through the current collaboration with the end user. Indeed, a product related to team and defect management (only in 2D) is currently being implemented. During these product specifications and implementation that will be enriched with the outputs of the ARTwin project, the discussions and on site meetings with the partner have given Artefacto the ability to get the required knowledge in order to define the requirements and user stories described in this document.

Upon discussion with the partners and further deliberations with the factory and construction sites in context, the user stories will provide the baseline for the implementation. Supporting documents such as UI style guides, details on technical features, workflows, standards, and so on will also be detailed in subsequent deliverables.

Note: It is understood that the use case details and subsequently the specific user stories may evolve during the project. The functional or non-functional requirements may evolve accordingly, or the parameters may be adapted. These adjustments will primarily be done as and when the specifications for the use case demonstrators are finalized as part of Work Package 5 deliverables.

2 System Features

This section describes the identified use cases pertaining to this project and its subsequently detailed user stories. Furthermore, technical features, constraints and opportunities are outlined with respect to each use case.

2.1 Use cases

2.1.1 Use Case 1: AR enabled factory worker: Provide contextually and spatial correct augmentation information in factories

Use case summary

- Shop floor personnel can instantly retrieve contextual information on the machines they interact with
- As production lines and factory layouts are constantly and dynamically changing, the map of the layout needs to be continuously updated in real time for consumption
- All relevant information w.r.t to both the machines and the layout and their interdependencies is aggregated and can be presented in one view

Summary of technical features to achieve

Current digital twins of production systems
Hands-free consumption of above relevant info via mobile AR devices
Objects in context are accurately identified and displayed in appropriate position and is interactable
Complex contextual data and layout info to be made available on mobile AR devices
Both static and dynamic information should be made available
Dynamic and on demand retrieval of plant/shop floor layouts in 3D
Collective view of all associated equipment and infrastructure interdependencies to be presented in one glance
Additional data sources can be both real-time simulation models and recorded materials from multiple operators

User stories

As a shop floor worker/quality check staff/ maintenance personnel, I want to be able to check the completion and verify the quality of a machine/part/object produced

Priority: 1

Scenario/workflow description:

- Inspection/ Maintenance personnel goes to machine/part/object and gets AR assisted guidance which can be additional info on an HMD to help them conduct quality checks.

Other remarks

- Frequency of complex maintenance tasks is once a year
- There are about 30-40 workers per site doing visual inspections tasks.
- The visual inspection shifts for individual workers can be 8h and collaborative workshops range between 1-2h
- Currently only static screens assist in visual inspection
- On the machine level- if it's a regular maintenance, then the workers know exactly what to do
- Restrictions on data privacy, workers' rights will be a key factor

As a factory operator/supervisor, I want to see an overall updated status of all worker tasks and associated machines to plan tasks to be delegated accurately

Priority: 2

Scenario/workflow description:

- Data is collected from multiple sources and is visualized collectively/cumulatively on an HMD/handheld device which shows an overall view of the factory site progress

Other remarks

- Collection and syncing of data from multiple sources would be a challenge due to data privacy and Information security regulations. ACP ratings must be done, and permissions must be acquired.
- Databases are protected by firewalls which may be tough to get into
- The real benefit comes from syncing and showing "relevant" data. Visualization would just be an add on.
- Dashboards showing KPIs, cycle time, information on maintenance status and so on are already shown on the sites on different static screens.

Additional use cases considerations

As an additional note, the following use cases were considered and discussed but may not be applicable for the ARTwin project due to the reasons specified below:

Use Case scenario “Standard work instructions with AR guidance”

- As workers in the Siemens target factories already know exactly what to do and are highly experienced, such guidance applications may not be necessary
- Newer employees or students could learn the tasks very quickly within 10-15 min. And here, too, there is no extra need for AR assisted guidance.

Use case scenario “Navigational workflows”

- The workers also know where to go. Normally, they have smartwatches to visualize error codes or get notifications on rooms where they must perform tasks. These are also routine tasks and therefore, extra AR assisted guidance is not required.

2.1.2 Use Case 2: “Dynamic Production Line Planning”: Leverage an always accurate 3D factory layout to enable flexibility and automation required in Industry 4.0 production

Use case summary

- As production systems and plant layouts are changing dynamically and frequently, there is a need to adapt and reconfigure the shop floor as quickly as possible
- Therefore, the plant managers, or production planners need updated and exact maps of shop floor layouts and associated machinery to flexibly plan any dynamic changes to the production floor
- In most cases, there will not be a design environment from the beginning. Therefore, it is essential to start designing from scratch.
- Currently it is being done with the help of Virtual Reality technologies. The use of MR or AR technologies need to have a clear benefit and be convincing for the factory sites to adopt the same.
- Demonstrator will be installed in a Siemens lead factory for Industry 4.0 and will leverage the ARtwin technologies to showcase dynamic production line planning

Broad technical features to achieve

Accurate and updated maps of factory layout
Accurate and updated position and orientation of shop floor equipment
Flexible simulation and reconfiguration of production systems
Planning for new production batches take into context both requirements for its own line as well as obscured areas by other lines
AR/VR tools enable (re)planning via 3D visualizations and interactions of production system digital twins

Alterations made on-site via the AR/VR interface to communicate and update itself back and forth with input from backend simulations and feedback from other operators/supervisors elsewhere

User stories

As a production engineer/planner, I want to keep up with updating factory layouts in real-time so that I can reconfigure or plan new production batches accurately and flexibly

As a plant manager, I want to know how much available space is on the shop floor, in order to fit in new equipment

As a hardware designer, I want to visualize mock-ups from my Teamcenter™ database and see how the assembly works with the environment

As a layout designer/construction designer/robot programming expert, I want to ensure my robots on the shop floor reach every designated location in the planning stage

As a shop floor operator, I want to visualize the space constraints for my workstations

As a plant manager, I want to visualize and optimize planning with digital mock-ups, analyse the data and reconfigure if need be, simultaneously in the real world

The above user stories have been grouped because of the overlapping possibilities of implementation

Priority: 1

Scenario/workflow description:

- AR device makes changes to machine which links up to backend simulations and visualizes changes real-time
- Typically starts with an existing 3D representation of the layout to be planned. The scanned machines are replaced with CAD versions and then this planning activity takes place
- There are manual and robotic stations to perform certain tasks in a factory site. Robots do special steps of the production processes. Manual stations with humans prepare assembly steps and workpieces go over to the next stations, some of which are robotic. They then perform a step and then it moves to the next station which can be manual or robotic and so on. While planning, it is essential to check if the robots and humans can reach all designated areas and if there is enough space to move around to perform their tasks. Therefore, the visualization in AR and planning is required.
- There are also cardboard mock-ups prepared, where lining of physical cardboard boxes is done to plan a mock-up of workstations and see if there is enough space for them. This is then compared with any 3D scans of the real world however in 2D and tested back in the real world. This creates a gap in the analysis and the reconfiguration phase which are done separately. Therefore, it would be preferred to do this simultaneously on the factory site.

Other remarks

- As VR technologies to perform planning is already being used, it may be a challenge to convince AR to be beneficial. AR planning could be beneficial if there is no 3D representation of a plant already
- It would be desired to visualize the digital robots or AGVs in the AR world and see the digital planning status and do the configurations parallelly
- 5-6 people typically perform this task
- Highly dynamic environment. For example, 10.000m² area has changes every year in 25% of its equipment. Most factories are brown field factories and change a lot. About 115 changes a year with almost 30% reconfiguration in layout planning
- Production lines assembly lines are bigger – 2.5 w x15 l x 2.5 h (meters)

2.1.3 Use case 3: Better constructions with AR

Use case summary

In order to minimize costs and time, on a construction site:

- It is necessary to help the workers to limit the defects to avoid solving them after pouring the concrete.
- If defects happen, it is also necessary to help the workers detecting them in order to solve them early.

For that purpose, it is necessary:

- (1) to help the workers to better understand the things to be done,
 - (2) to help the workers detecting the predictable defects in order to adjust the forms before pouring the concrete (ie., with validating that reservations of doors / windows / networks / etc. are well located in the forms)
- And (3) to help the workers reporting the effective defects after pouring the concrete in order to solve them during construction.

Demonstrations will be done on a Eiffage Bretagne construction site located in Dinard (inside a defects reporting tool that is currently being implemented)

Broad technical features to achieve

Accurate and updated map of the construction site that is every day changing
Accurate and updated position and orientation of the reference BIM model on the construction site so, as to provide: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accurate (precision <= 5cm) localization of the end users in order allow efficient BIM visualization in AR (to prepare the forms)

- Automatic detection of the predictable defects before pouring the concrete (to adjust the forms)
- Automatic detection of the effective defects after pouring the concrete (to report them in the dedicated reporting tool)
- Automatic computation of the construction progress by comparing the reference BIM model and the map of the construction site

Project manager, form workers, builder will be impacted by the solution that will be implemented during the ARTwin project

User stories

As project or site manager, technical lead, I want to see if construction is realized without defects (global view)

As project or site manager, technical lead, I want to know the construction progress (global view)

As a project or site manager, technical lead, form worker or builder, I want to know what to do in the selected form (local view)

As a project or site manager, technical lead, form worker or builder, I want to know if the form is correct before pouring the concrete (local view)

As a project or site manager, technical lead, form worker or builder, I want to know if there are defects after the concrete being poured (local view)

2.2 System level requirements

2.2.1 Functional requirements

The project deliverables can be broadly outlined into the following features deliverables. These have already been defined in depth in the project introductory brief (Artwin_Part_B_Section1-3_v5.pdf). Therefore, only a broad overview is presented below.

A unified and standardized map of the factory or construction site

- Digital representation (map pivot) of current state of various elements
- Pivot shared by connected services
- Updated in real-time
- Various input data sources

Deliverable:

- Build a map corresponding to an area of 250m² updated in real-time by at least 3 devices as soon as elements are moving.

A real-time and robust localization for AR services

- Large scale real-time localization based on unified map
- Dynamic and adaptable to environment (changing light conditions, occlusions, etc)

Deliverable:

- Relocalize an AR device in an area of 250m² with position accuracy < 5cm and an orientation accuracy <2°.

A distributed computation based on edge and cloud computing

- Optimize workload over nodes available in factory and construction site's internal network

Deliverable:

- Re/place dynamically the service (Relocalization, mapping, rendering) on a distributed cloud (device, local case, central cloud).
- Re/placement "handover" time within the second, including function and data.
- Ideal target of <500ms and shall be done without visible service impact

Real-time update of digital twin based on unified map

- 3D scene change detection
- User visual localization
- 3D structure change detection based on RGBD sensing
- Semantic understanding and labelling

Deliverable:

- AR refinement and VR labelling highlighting differences in AR/VR within 5 sec
- Simple annotations in AR/VR within 10 sec
- Accuracy of entity labelling within 20 cm
- Updated map provision within 3 sec after commit
- Working range of 250m² per working area
- Switching time between work areas 10 sec
- VR labelling: Jumping to locations with differences in VR under 5 sec
- Complex annotations within 1 min
- Accuracy of labelling within 5 cm

Display complex augmentation on low-resources AR devices

- Overcome limitation of computing power of existing and future devices

Deliverable:

- Render complex 3D scene containing more than 40 million polygons at more than 40 fps
- Latency < 20ms

Easily deploy ARTwin platform in the field

- 5G edge cloud case with local cloud storage, cloud processing and radio communication capabilities

Deliverable:

- Deploy in < 1h the ARTwin platform in any factory or construction site

2.2.2 Design and Implementation Constraints

From the interviews and research conducted with the personnel directly or indirectly involved with the Siemens factory sites, the following list of factors/constraints have been identified. These apply to the two use cases “AR enabled factory worker” and “Dynamic Production Line Planning”. Please refer to [Section 2.1](#) for more details on the use cases.

Site area

Very likely indoor sites. Outdoor sites are very seldom and if so, only partially

Dynamicity

Range of the area in context is anywhere between 100 m² to 10.000 m² with separate halls and galleries. Sometimes there are bridges to connect from one area to the other. And in some other areas there are basements. There is also typically just 1 level.

The area range for the dynamic production line planning use case is typically 600m².

Lighting

Mostly synthetic lighting which is overhead. Natural light is coming from windows but there are fewer windows. Warehouses are not lit that well. Thus, quality and homogeneity may vary over areas. Sometimes, the lighting is made to be synthetically even by introducing extra equipment to influence that. The lighting mostly varies over areas and not over time, which means even during non-shift hours, the lights would probably be on.

Network availability

Usually at least 1 dedicated Wi-Fi coverage available everywhere except for some cut-off areas like basements, etc. Bandwidth is an issue and not high. Therefore, streaming video calls and the likes may not be possible. Other networks are usually locked with firewalls and are difficult to get into.

3D data reproduction

For the use cases specified above, there can be 3 different scales of 3D data to consider. Please note that the remaining factors are explained in context to the scales outlined here:

1. Overall factory scale: The 3D scans produce a lot of data. They are usually POI (points of interest) or Autodesk Recap formats. CAD models are produced from existing tools like PlantSimulator™, ProcessSimulate™, Tecnomatix™ etc. These are also provided mostly from external suppliers. Machines which are physically 1mx2m are represented as a cube, polygon with 10 facets and are simple iconic models with basic colours.
2. Production line / Assembly scale: Area range can be 20mx4mx5m for example. Finer, more detailed CAD models of produced machines
3. Individual machine scale: Area is usually 1mx2m of machines. Representation in CAD is down to nuts and bolts level. The 3D formats of the machines, parts or any objects would be. step or. fbx

The machines used are both big and small and of carrying sizes.

The formats for workflow metadata would usually be JSON or XML.

The images localized or any other data sources having images would be usually JPEG or PNG formats

Coordinates would be formatted in meters in world space equivalent.

Existing text labels or QR codes would be used as markers for localization/tracking purposes

Wherever possible, the 3D models of the machines or objects can be obtained from the suppliers. The Siemens partners will ensure these are provided. Normally, information on geometry is included in such Cad models from the suppliers. However, depending on the use case and context, this needs to be made lighter (polygon count). In case of any objects or machines to be scanned, then explicit permission shall be acquired before the scans are performed. The same holds good for the 3D scans of the factory sites to be performed. Not all factory sites have 3D scans or maps already available.

Localization

For the above scales mentioned, technologies for localization should most likely be device SLAM + GPS for (1).

For (2) and (3), device SLAM, Cad model reference for edge-based realignment for example, scanning of existing markers, barcodes/labels to re-localize

The overall preferred approach is most likely unique feature recognition via scanning markers/labels or any other identification methods + device SLAM

The Relocalization frequency depends on task in context and type of device. This shall be narrowed down when the exact user story and task is defined.

Examples of Relocalization frequency would be HMDs more often for static tasks (inspection for example) and less often for dynamic tasks (machine maintenance for example)

The precision of localization should be > 10cm

Tracking

For the above scales mentioned, size of object to track would usually be 10 cm or more.

For (1), tracking different machines in the factory layout, mobile machines such as forklifts, carts etc. should also be considered. The number of objects in this case are > 100 machines

For (2), tracking different machines on the production line should be possible. The number of objects in this case should be > 100 machines on the production line

For (3), tracking down to the level of nuts and bolts on the machine should be considered. The number of objects to be tracked in this case should be > 100 parts on that machine

Reflectivity could be an issue for tracking as there would be tiny, round, metal parts which are shiny and grey

Occlusion issues also play a role. In the case of (1), some machines are occluded by a concrete pillar. So there are chances of a model not being able to be visualized completely. For (3), not so much of an issue, if you have any tools in hand and may not be frequently occluding the machines to be tracked

Occlusion by workers would not be an issue

Movement speed of workers, machines etc. is pedestrian speed

The confidence level of tracking or localization should be around 10 cm

Sometimes, the parts are palm sized. Smallest area to be tracked could be around 1m² area.

Immersive experience

There would be multi-devices depending on the use case in context. Most likely will be iOS, Android or HoloLens.

For the AR enabled worker use case, it will most likely be AR technology. There will also be mostly 1-2 users pertaining to this use case.

For the Dynamic production line planning use case, it will most likely be both VR and AR technologies. There will also be mostly 6-7 users pertaining to this use case, collaboratively working together in workshops. These workshops are typically all morning/all afternoon sessions and are more frequently held. The frequency of such workshops are usually 2-3 times a week.

For continuity of the immersive experience through areas/spaces, it may most likely be not existing since navigational use cases are ruled out currently. The workers would know exactly where to go or are already being advised on where to go and hence continuity would not be such a high factor.

The duration of the entire experience likes between 5-30 min depending on the exact task at hand. However, maximum of 5-10 min usage is envisioned for HMDs in AR like HoloLens.

Large scale visualization for areas defined earlier under Site area is required

Large scale localization for scales defined previously is required

The persistency of the 3D maps and AR content is required, and duration is dependent on use case and type of device used.

Devices in the field would be smartphones (iOS, Android), tablets (iOS, Windows), HMDs (HoloLens, HTC Vive)

General preference is to have one platform-based applications

Different roles have different devices. Typically, a manager has tablets (for example: iPad Air) and repair technicians have another

Interaction methods

Interaction will mostly be touch based. External devices like pens, clickers, styluses could also be considered. These devices would mostly be for annotations or measurement tasks in specific.

Many workers will have gloves so that needs to be a factor.

Hands-free interaction is mostly preferred, because workers will have to handle the machines or objects.

Voice interaction is ruled out since there are regional accents and lot of environmental noise which may prevent any voice commands from being recognized correctly.

Gestures with eyes for example, gaze to complete any action could also be a possibility

Multi-gesture combination input could also be a possibility

Reference coordinate systems

The coordinate systems depend on use cases. If there is any navigation, then it will most likely be GPS. For factory hall scans, assembly line tasks and for individual machine tasks- the usual AR world coordinate systems (in meters) would be preferred.

At least 2 coordinate systems would have to be considered

Unifying coordinate systems could be desired.

Service support

Since data stored in the cloud is usually sceptically received, edge servers would be preferred.

Connection to internal systems and databases, such as Teamcenter, NX, and so on holding key information about the processes may be required. However, getting access to such systems may be difficult and is always subject to ACP regulations. These shall be clarified by Siemens partners and factory site personnel.

The constraints that apply to the use case, “Better constructions with AR” are identified below:

Site area

Fully Indoor / Outdoor sites.

Dynamicity

Range of the area in context is anywhere between 100 m² to 10.000 m² with many floors.

Lighting

Synthetic and Natural light should be considered with many times very bad lighting conditions.

Network availability

Usually one dedicated Wi-Fi in a restricted area with 3G/4G everywhere except for some cut-off areas like basements, etc. Bandwidth/latency are an issue but not high.

3D data reproduction

For the use cases specified above, there can be many scales to be considered regarding the selected parts of the BIM model that could be of high resolution in case a global view is required. Materials and texture are not really an issue but can also be considered. 3D scan is not possible as it should require adding new procedure and tools in the workflow. Also this could be too much expensive regarding the envisioned product. Some reference image can be considered.

Localization

For the above scales mentioned, technologies for localization should most likely be device SLAM, GPS, IMU, BIM model reference for edge-based realignment for example, scanning of images references to re-localize. The precision of localization should be < 5cm.

Tracking

For the above scales mentioned, size of object to track would usually be from various sizes up to the building itself. Everything that could help a precise localization in any context is helpful. Reflectivity is not really an issue except in bad weather conditions. Occlusion could be an issue sometimes especially during validation of finished work. Occlusion by workers would not be an issue. Movement speed of workers, etc. is mostly pedestrian speed for the targeted use case. The confidence level of tracking or localization should be less than 5 cm.

Immersive experience

There would be multi-devices depending on the use case in context. Most likely will be iOS, Android or HoloLens and possibly real or any other relevant devices. AR most likely to be considered. There will also be sometime multiusers experience to be provided if collaborative work is required. The duration of the entire experience likes between 5-30 min depending on the exact task at hand. However, maximum of 5-10 min usage is envisioned for HMDs in AR like HoloLens. Large scale visualization for areas defined earlier under Site area is required. Large scale localization for scales defined previously is required/ The persistency of the 3D maps and AR content is required, and duration is dependent on use case and type of device used. Devices in the field would be smartphones (iOS, Android), tablets (iOS, Windows), HMDs (HoloLens, etc.)

Interaction methods

Interaction will mostly be touch based. Within headsets, hands-free interaction is mostly preferred, because workers will have to handle the objects. Gestures with eyes for example, gaze to complete any action could also be a possibility. Multi-gesture combination input could also be a possibility.

Reference coordinate systems

The coordinate systems should include GPS/elevation. At least 2 coordinate systems would have to be considered (the SIG and the local coordinate regarding the project localization). Unifying coordinate systems could be desired.

Service support

Edge servers and distant cloud servers can be considered.

Furthermore, the subsequent success criterion for the use case “Better constructions with AR” must be considered:

- Information on defects should be instantly retrievable
- BIM should be visualized in VR/AR
- Defects should be detected automatically in VR/AR
- Localization precision in AR should be $\leq 5\text{cm}$ (higher precision is required) in order to manage efficiently the defects
- Construction progress should be computed automatically by comparing reality with the BIM reference model

2.2.3 Documentation

User documentation: It shall be clarified with the factory site personnel if any user documentation is needed in the event of the technology being used in the production environment. For demo purposes, the documentation can be written (.docx) or video formats.

Technical documentation: The implementation partners are requested to document the technology and corresponding software, tools, methodologies and other data deem fit into the technical documents.

2.2.4 Requirements from external projects

To better understand the requirements of the manufacturing industry for augmented reality technology, the ETSI Industry Specification Group “Augmented reality Framework” has carried out an online questionnaire in the period between February 28th and May 1st 2018. Altogether, 77 persons from 16 countries responded to the questionnaire (43% from Germany, 24% from France, 5% from Canada, 5% from USA, 5% from Spain, 5% from Italy).

The questions covered the targeted use cases, usage conditions and environments, and barriers to deployment. As regards the ARCloud project, here is what we can retain:

- 34% of participants identified the tracking as the major challenge of augmented reality (13% for tracking accuracy, 11% for tracking robustness, 10% for relocalization issue), 29% identified the ergonomic, 11% the cost, and 9% the data.
- 39% of use cases are “Room scale”, 24% are “Desktop scale”, 18% are “Warehouse scale”, and 8% are “World scale”. Warehouse and world scale are more particularly required for manufacturing tasks and inspection/quality tasks.

- 65% of the participants want the AR user to have his hands-free (100% for training and manufacturing tasks).
- 73% of participants want a registration accuracy of few millimetre or under (100% for inspection, training and manufacturing tasks, 57% for maintenance task).
- In 88% of the cases, a viewing distance of less than 5 meters to the object is required (44% close to hand).
- 41% expect collaborative augmented reality.
- In 57% of the cases, the target use to track the AR system model evolves over time (e.g. step by step assembly).
- In 37% of the cases, the scene is dynamic with moving objects or persons.

In parallel of this questionnaire, the ETSI ISG ARF has organized two workshops (in Berlin and Paris) during which 13 players were able to share their AR experiences and requirements.

The full report including a survey on manufacturing industry requirements is published by the ETSI ISG ARF on the following address:

https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ARF/001_099/002/01.01.01_60/gr_ARF002v010101p.pdf

In order to further develop AR interoperability requirements, The AREA and the ETSI ISG ARF are currently collaborating by interviewing more than twenty international stakeholders, including hardware providers, software providers, application developers and end-users. It is still too early to draw conclusions, but it is clear from the first interviews that improved interoperability between the functions used by an augmented reality system will be crucial for its adoption. In addition, a two-day workshop organized by the H2020 CSA XR4ALL project, The ETSI ISG ARF and the AREA is scheduled for March 5 and 6, 2020 in the conference centre of Siemens in Munich. A whole day will be devoted to the subjects of interoperability and standardization for AR technologies.

3 External Interface Requirements

3.1 User Interfaces

The following general UI interface guidelines apply for the project deliverables:

- Wherever possible, uniform UI assets should be used across multiple platforms and devices to maintain homogeneity.
- Unity 3D software is the preferred tool for the UI interface screens. This is compatible with all the chosen platforms and devices outlined in the Operating Environment Section 2.4.2
- The 3D environment and the interaction modes should be emphasized on and taken advantage of. UI screens which look more like 2D interfaces should be avoided
- Interactions and number of steps to achieve a goal should be kept minimal.

- Users should be allowed to control position and orientation of the objects in 3D space (6 DOF – degrees of freedom)
- UI should be designed keeping in mind the Design and Implementation Constraints in Section 2.4.1

3.2 Hardware Interfaces

The AR devices shall provide an access to the frames captured by the built-in vision sensors, with a timestamp corresponding to the capture time (accurate to the millisecond).

The AR device should provide an access to the data captured by the inertial measurement unit with a timestamp corresponding to the capture time. Also, the AR devices should provide an access to the calibration parameters for each vision sensor (intrinsic, extrinsic and distortion parameters).

For the Remote rendering framework, a Wi-Fi connection with a large bandwidth range is desired for both uploads and downloads. Around 5MB with HD stereoscopic is desired for bandwidth. The latency shall be 10ms roundtrip time, in the event of without rendering. Furthermore, every device needs its own cloud instance. As per the resources for one instance, a high-end GPU is requested (for example NVIDIA GEFORCE, TESLA DRID GPU, ...). The range from the Wi-Fi router shall be within 20-50m with no obstacles in between. For the Relocalization frequency, 30-60 frames per second is desired for HMDs.

3.3 Software Interfaces

The operating systems would most likely be iOS and Windows as devices in consideration are Apple and Windows tablets. The SDKs would be ARKit and Windows SDK respectively. In addition, Windows is also applicable to the HMDs of choice which are the Microsoft HoloLens and HTC Vive.

Depending on devices allowed and cleared to be used on the factory sites, there is also a possibility of Android devices. In this case, the SDK would be ARCore.

Regarding construction sites the OS considered will be iOS (ARKit), Android(ARCore), Windows(Hololens 2). Some other interesting devices like the nReal glasses will be also considered during the project.

The AR SDK shall provide an access to the estimated pose of the AR device for each frame, or at least for keyframes. Also, the unity plugin of the AR SDK shall provide a means of overloading the pose of the virtual camera(s) simulating the viewpoint of the user (for optical see-through display) or of the camera (for video see-through display).

The AR device should provide an access to the 3D sparse point cloud with associated descriptors built by the SLAM implementation, and ideally, a way to compute descriptors used by the AR SDK for a set of key points extracted within an image.

For the Remote rendering framework, every edge node needs at least one Virtual Machine with Windows 10 Professional OS including Nvidia Grid.

3.4 Communications Interfaces

The Remote rendering framework supported by Holo Light GmbH is based on WebRTC. Therefore, it is desired that UDP (User Datagram protocol) is desired and the network shall be open to such types of data transmission. Also, a peer to peer connection with static IP is needed.

4 Non-functional Requirements

4.1 Performance Requirements

The desired performance of the applications is described in detail in [Section 2.4.1](#)

4.2 Safety Requirements

The devices and technologies used should be keeping in consideration the workers' rights and safety regulations. For example, the maximum usage of HMDs or devices close to the body shall be limited to 5-30 minutes. There would be safety clearances which would have to be obtained before its usage in a production environment. For the purposes of a demo, it should be limited usage to maximum of 30 minutes continuously.

4.3 Security Requirements

The Siemens factory sites have very strict regulations and data privacy policies. Furthermore, Information Security rules and worker's rights will also heavily play a role. Therefore, any access to data must be subjected to ACP (Asset classification and protection). This shall be conducted in conjunction with the Siemens representatives for the project and the factory partners in context. The usage, accessibility and duration of the data streams to be used by the project shall also be clearly identified and protocolled after the factory sites have been narrowed down.

Another point to consider is that, due to these strict security requirements, any external equipment to be installed to monitor or perform any activities would not be possible. In any event, any installation of partner equipment for the projects should always be consulted with the Siemens partners who will in turn obtain permission from the factory site in-charge.

The opportunities for a global view are also limited and will be subjected to only a certain area or space cordoned off for demo purposes for the ARTwin project.

4.4 Software Quality Attributes

Detailed acceptance criteria will be defined for the specific software deliverables and outlined for each shortlisted user story. These shall however be defined in the next versions of the requirement specification document. Factors such as adaptability, availability, correctness, flexibility, interoperability, maintainability, portability, reliability, reusability, robustness, testability, and usability shall be also clearly defined and quantified in subsequent editions to this document.

5 Other Requirements

The standardization and legal aspects of the requirements would be discussed during the project and will be made part of Work Package 5 deliverables.

6 Conclusions

The task 2.2 deliverable which is the requirements specification document for the ARTwin project aims to outline and clarify the use cases and user stories which are to be focused on and implemented as part of this project. It is thereby also understood that this document will evolve with its requirements and the parameters will be eventually adapted. These adjustments will primarily be done as and when the specifications for the use case demonstrators are finalized as part of Work package 5 deliverables in the project. In line of this, this document is made available to all the ARTwin project partners with as much input as possible at this early stage of the project.

Appendix A: Glossary

Abbreviations and definitions

3D Tracking is the process of estimating the pose (position and orientation) at time t of a real-world object or of an AR device knowing its pose at time $t-1$.

AR (Augmented Reality). MR (mixed reality) is the ability to mix in real-time spatially registered digital content with the real world.

ARCloud (Augmented Reality Cloud) aims to compute and store in the cloud a complete cartography of the real-world used both for visualization and for accurate localization.

BIM (Building Information Modeling) is a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility. A BIM is a shared knowledge resource for information about a facility forming a reliable basis for decisions during its life cycle; defined as existing from earliest conception to demolition².

Digital Twin is a virtual representation of a physical product or process, used to understand and predict the physical counterpart's performance characteristics.

Mapping is the process of building a 3D map of the real environment generally used for localizing one or a set of vision sensors.

Relocalization is the process of estimating the pose of a device at time t based on a knowledge of the real environment, but without any knowledge of its pose at time $t-1$.

AGVs: Automated Guidance Vehicles – is a portable robot that follows along marked long lines or wires on the floor, or uses radio waves, vision cameras, magnets, or lasers for navigation.

Appendix B : Interview Consent Form Sample

ARTWIN
INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

“An AR cloud and digital twins solution for industry and construction 4.0”

Project Acronym:	ARtwin
Programme:	HORIZON2020
Topic:	ICT-25-2018-2020 - Interactive Technologies
Type of Action:	Research and Innovation Action
Start day:	01/10/2019
Duration:	36 months

Interview Information Sheet

ISSUED BY: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

ISSUE DATE: 08/11/2019

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Information Sheet

ARTwin: “An AR cloud and digital twins solution for industry and construction 4.0”

Introduction

We would like to invite you to take part to an interview that is being carried out by ARTwin, a 3-year project funded by the European Union within the framework of the H2020 Research and Innovation programme. Before you decide to participate, we would like to inform you why this interview is being conducted and what it will involve for you. Please take the time to read this information sheet carefully and do not hesitate to ask questions about anything you do not understand. Talk to others about the interview if you wish.

What is the ARTwin project all about?

Lifecycle processes are becoming increasingly digital while Digital Twin and Building Information Modelling (BIM) action plans are gaining ground in Europe. **Industry and Construction 4.0** have high expectations from **Augmented Reality (AR)** technologies in terms of **productivity gains** and **quality improvement**. However, the early-stage AR Cloud implementations do not fully meet Industry and Construction 4.0 requirements and European players may face a lock-in situation if no sovereign solution is proposed to them. Thus, ARTwin aims to provide European Industry and Construction 4.0 with an **AR Cloud platform** that meets their needs. This platform will be deployed on a private distant or edge cloud, ensuring the privacy of information while offering the following key services:

- ✚ A **3D map update service** of any factory or construction site;
- ✚ Accurate and robust **3D registration of any AR device** in large-scale and dynamic environments, allowing to present relevant information to workers at the right time and place, including complex 3D augmentations remotely rendered;
- ✚ Continuous **real-time maintenance of the Digital Twin of a factory or BIM of construction site** based on vision sensors;

The ARTwin platform and services will be deployed and validated in operational environments through **pilot use cases in both manufacturing and construction**. In this respect, the ARTwin pilots involve:

Two use cases in Industry 4.0; “*AR enabled factory worker*” – Provide contextually and spatially correct augmentation information in factories; “*Dynamic production line planning*” – Leverage an accurate 3D factory layout to enable flexibility and automation required in Industry 4.0 production.

One use case in Construction 4.0; “*Better constructions with AR*” – Provide multi-user AR tools in order to help workers during constructions. For more information on the partners and your participation in the interview, please review the [Annexure](#) after the [Informed Consent form](#).

Informed Consent Form

ARTwin

“An AR cloud and digital twins solution for industry and construction 4.0”

Please complete this form after you have read the Information Sheet and/or listened to an explanation about the research.

I confirm that I understand that by ticking/initialling each box below I am consenting to this element of the study. I understand that it will be assumed that unticked/uninitialled boxes means that I DO NOT consent to that part of the study. I understand that by not giving consent for any one element I may be deemed ineligible for the study.

✓ I have read and understood the Information Sheet with which I was provided. I have been given a full explanation of the nature, purpose, location and likely duration of the interview, and of what will be expected from me in its context.

✓ I have had an opportunity to consider what information will be expected of me. I have also had the opportunity to ask questions which have been answered to my satisfaction.

✓ I understand that my personal data will be held and processed in confidence and in accordance with the principles laid out by GDPR.

✓ I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without the need to justify my decision.

✓ I confirm that I have read and understood the above and freely consent to participate in the interview. I have been given adequate time to consider my participation.

✓ I am aware of whom I should contact if I wish to lodge a complaint.

If you would like your contact details to be retained so that you can be contacted in the future by the project researchers who would like to invite you to participate in further activities of this project, or in future studies of a similar nature, please tick the appropriate box below.

NO, I would not like to be contacted

YES, I would be happy to be contacted

Name of **interviewee** (*BLOCK CAPITALS*):.....

Signature:

Date:

Place:

Name of **person receiving consent** (*BLOCK CAPITALS*):

Signature:

Date:

Place:

ANNEX

Who are the partners participating in the ARTwin project?

The ARTwin project brings together a consortium of 7 partners across 4 different European countries (Greece, France, Germany, Czech Republic), as follows:

- **Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC**, Greece (ARTwin coordinator): An innovation consulting company actively involved in the European R&I landscape, providing business and innovation support services to private and public organisations across several industries and market sectors. For more information visit <https://qplan-intl.gr/>.
- **B<>COM**, France: A Technology Research Institute involved in advancing, enabling and delivering Technologies in the field of Hypermedia (virtual/augmented reality, immersive interactions, advanced media formats, user experience and acceptability), Networks and Security (future network architectures and interfaces) and e-Health (connected healthcare, augmented healthcare). More information at: <https://b-com.com>.
- **SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT**, Germany: A Global powerhouse in electronics and electrical engineering, as well as a major Industry 4.0 actor. Siemens operates in the fields of automation, electrification and digitisation, while it holds leading market positions in all of its business areas. For further information please visit: <https://new.siemens.com/global>.
- **CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE**, Czech Republic: A leading academic institution in the fields of computer vision, machine learning and robotics, participating in Industry 4.0 activities and connected to global industries. It is primarily concerned with fundamental and applied research as well as education of engineers and researches. It also accumulates knowledge and provides it to industries and society, in order to support business and administration. More information at: <https://www.cvut.cz>.
- **NOKIA BELL LABS FRANCE**, France: A global leader in communication services, as well as in 5G and cloud technologies. Offers enabling infrastructure for 5G, Internet of Things, emerging applications in virtual reality and digital health. Possesses expertise in analytics, cloud, optics and wireless technologies and collaborates actively with the innovation community. More at: <https://www.bell-labs.com>.
- **HOLO-INDUSTRIE 4.0 SOFTWARE GMBH**, Germany: A company which creates practical and professional software applications for leading industry players in areas like engineering, manufacturing, design, services and utilities, as well as training. HOLO-INDUSTRIE also pioneers in tackling the biggest issues, expressing the potential of AR by developing deep tech and 5G infrastructure. For more information please visit: <https://www.holo-light.com/>.
- **ARTEFACTO SAS**, France: A company which specialises on developing AR technologies for construction purposes. Artefacto is structured and divided into business units addressing 4 core fields such as: Real Estate (including architecture & urban planning), industry, museography and media entertainment. More at: <https://www.artefacto-ar.com>.

Why have I been invited to take part to this interview?

You have been invited to take part in this interview because you have been identified as a key stakeholder and potential end-user for ARTwin. In this context, we would like to learn more about your views about the:

- ✚ Desired features and functionalities of the ARTwin platform and its services;
- ✚ Implementation concept of the ARTwin pilot use cases.

This will help us to better shape the project's cloud platform and its services to your needs, as well as design well-tailored pilot use cases.

Is my participation voluntary?

Your participation is entirely voluntary. There will be no adverse consequences if you decide not to participate or withdraw at a later stage. In fact, you may withdraw your participation at any time, as well as request for your data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. If you withdraw from the interview, any identifiable data already collected will be retained only if you allow us to. Anonymous data already collected will be used because we cannot trace the information back to you. No further data would be collected, or any other procedure would be carried out in relation to you.

What will my involvement in this interview require?

If you agree to take part in this interview, we will ask you to sign an Informed Consent Form and you will be given this Information Sheet to keep along with a copy of your signed Informed Consent Form. The project will last for 36 months but your involvement would only be for as long as you wish. During this time, you may be asked to participate, if you wish, in workshops that will be held by the ARTwin project. You are free to decline to participate in any of these activities, as you wish.

How will you handle my data?

Your data will be held in complete confidence and we will follow ethical and legal practice in relation to all interview procedures. Personal data (such as your name, contact details, etc.) will be handled in accordance with the GDPR. Your personal data will be stored securely. You will not be identified in any reports/publications resulting from this interview and those reading them will not know who has contributed.

Are there any risks involved?

There are no risks involved in this study.

Will I benefit from this study?

By participating in this interview, you will be contributing towards the demand-driven development of the ARTwin services, platform specifications and use case requirements according to your needs. On top of that, you may get the chance to participate in future project activities, should you wish to, getting early access to the offerings of ARTwin.

Whom do I contact if there is a problem?

Any complaint or concern about any aspect of your experience during the course of the interview will be addressed. If you wish to complain, or have any concerns in this respect, then you should communicate with the ARTwin Coordinator, using the details provided below.

ARTwin Coordinator: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Contact person: Ms. Anastasia Matonaki

Phone: +30 2310 411191

Email: matonaki@qplan-intl.gr

Website: <https://qplan-intl.gr/>

Thank you for taking the time to read this Information Sheet!